
MARKETING ANALYSIS OF RICE IN UDU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF DELTA STATE,
NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study carried out an assessment of rice marketing in Udu local government area of Delta State. It specifically examined the socio-economic characteristics of the rice marketers in the study area; determined profitability of rice marketing and examined the market structure and conduct for rice in the study area. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 70 rice marketers in the study area and structured questionnaire administered on them. Descriptive statistics, gross margin, Gini-coefficient and production function analyses techniques were used to analyse the data collected. The study showed that 78.57% of the respondents belong to the active segment of the population of 40- 49%. The profitability analysis showed that an average marketer incurred an average total variable cost of N3, 015,838.57 per month but earned average revenue of N3, 314,320 per month which indicate that an average marketer earned N298, 481.43 as gross margin. A Gini coefficient of 0.4426 obtained in this study indicates a high level of concentration in the rice market. The result of the production function postulated for rice marketers in the study area reveals that the postulated regressors explained 94.44% in the variation of the regressand.

KEYWORDS; Marketing analysis, Rice, Market structure, Profitability, Delta

INTRODUCTION

Rice is an important annual crop in Nigeria. It is one of the major staples, which can provide a nation's population with the nationally required food security minimum of 2,400 calories per person per day (FAO, 2000).

Rice is significant to the economy of many nations. It is a major source of revenue in the United States and Southern Europe; a staple diet in Japan and mainstay of the economies of China, Indonesia, Thailand and Vietnam (Encarta, 2004). In sub-Saharan Africa, West African is the leading producer and consumer of rice (WARDA, 1996). Rice is a staple crop throughout West Africa, especially in Cote de Ivoire, the Gambia, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Burkina Faso, Senegal and Sierra Leone (NISER, 2002).

According to IRRI (2001) the crop is commonly consumed even as a food crop for household food security. The average Nigerian consumes 24.8 kg of rice per year, representing 9 % of annual calorie intake. Due to its increasing contribution to the per capita calorie consumption of Nigerians, the demand for rice has been increasing at a much faster rate than domestic production and more than in any other African countries since mid 1970s (FAO, 2001). For instance, during the 1960s, Nigeria had the lowest per capita annual consumption of rice in the West African sub-region with an annual average of 3 kg. Since then, Nigeria's per capital consumption levels have grown significantly at 7.3 per cent per annum. Consequently, per capital consumption during the 1980s increased to an annual average of 18 kg and reached 22kg between 1995-2000.

According to Bamidele, *et al* (2010) as a response to the prevailing rice supply deficit situation in Nigeria, successive Nigerian governments intervened in the rice sector by increasing tariffs so that local production could be encouraged. This was expected to widen the home market for the nation's local rice. The Government also established the Federal Rice Research Station (FRRS) at Badeggi in 1970 and the National Cereal Research Institute (NCRI) in 1974. Also established were the National Seed Service (NSS) with the assistance of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in 1975, and Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) in 1976. Other government programmes were the River Basin Development Authority (RDBA), Agricultural Development Projects (ADP), the National Grain Production Programmes (NGPP), the

Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAP), and the Presidential Initiative on Increased Rice Production, Processing and Export.

Bamidele *et al* (2010) noted that despite the numerous Nigerian government policies on rice, the demand–supply gap for rice still persists. Recent rice production figures from 2004 put national rice production at 2.96 million tonnes of paddy cultivated on an area of 1,595,840 hectares. This estimate established a yield of 1.82 metric tonnes per hectare and total milled rice of 1,480,168 tonnes giving a milling recovery rate of 51 % while total national demand of milled rice is estimated at 3.0 million tonnes per annum. There is therefore a deficit of 1,519,832 tonnes of milled rice. Estimates indicate that rice imports represent more than 25 per cent of agricultural imports and over 40 per cent of domestic consumption (FMARD, 2004).

Nigeria has thus become a major rice importer in the world market and second only to Indonesia in the last five years of this decade (2000-2005) of rice imports rose steadily from US \$259 million to US \$655 million and US \$756 million in 2001 and 2002, respectively (CBN, 2006). These estimates do not take into account the unrecorded smuggled rice imports into Nigeria (Rahji, 2005).

Olukosi and Isitor (1990) stated that a good and efficient marketing system promotes the pace of economic development by encouraging specialization, which leads to more output. The importance of agricultural and food markets for consumers, producers, national economies and international trade has always been and is expected to be extremely high.

Olomola (2005) stressed a need to improve the market structure and performance to enable farmers and agribusiness firms operate in a transparent and speculative business environment. Also Olomola (2001) it is imperative to put the enterprises on the path of improved performance may be well improved management actions, competitive restructuring, efficient marketing management. To improve competitiveness, there must be improved access to market information and physical facilities not only for traditional export crops but also for other crops of industrial importance such as yams, cassava, rice and sorghum.

Statement of the Problem

In the recent years, there has been a sharp rise in the prices of wheat and rice in India as well as the world. From a comfortable food situation, the world has suddenly woken up to a scramble for supplies and rising commodity prices. Food prices are crucial and can topple governments. Managing the food demand-supply and prices has become a serious concern, and the marketing system and its efficiency have become crucial. Poor efficiency in marketing has serious consequences for both producers and consumers as well as for the government budgets and the economy.(Gandhi,2008).

Adegeye and Dittoh (1985) also pointed out that transportation costs accounts for a large proportion of marketing cost. This situation may virtually increase the market price of agricultural commodities, and eventually reducing the market margins allocated to the farmers or the middlemen. For the middlemen, it may not be advantageous to the farmers and the consumers as they may tend to pull out of business.

However, in this study the following research questions need to be addressed:

- 1) What are the socio-economic characteristics of the rice marketers in the Study area?
- 2) What are the marketing functions performed by rice marketers in the study area?
- 3) What is the structure rice market in the study area?
- 4) Is rice marketing profitable in the study area?
- 5) What are the constraints of rice marketing in the study area?

Objective of the study

The general objective of this study is to analyze the marketing system of rice in Udu local government area of Delta State.

The specific objectives are to ;

1. Identify the socio-economic characteristic of the respondents in the study area.
2. Investigate the marketing functions and practices of respondents in the study area.

3. Describe rice market structure in the study area.
4. Evaluate costs and returns of rice marketing on the study area.
5. Identify the problem associated with the marketing of rice in the study area.

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis of the study stated in the null form is as follows:-

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between rice marketing cost and net returns of respondents.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was conducted in Udu local government area of Delta State. The local government area was created in August 27th 1991. Udu has common boundaries with her neighbours, Warri South, Uvwie, and Ughelli North and Warri-South West local Government Areas. The area falls into the rainforest zone and the vegetation consists of luxuriant deciduous and evergreen forest.

Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

A two stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the respondents; the first stage has a purposive sampling using the Jigbale main market. A complete enumeration of the rice marketers (trader) the market formed the sampling frame.

The second stage, 70 rice marketers were randomly selected from the market.

Method of Data Collection

The data for this study was obtained from primary and secondary sources. The primary data (field survey data) was obtained using personal interview and structured questionnaire that was administered to marketers in the study area. Data was collected on economic and demographic variables marketing and marketing information.

The secondary data was collected from journals, conference materials, textbooks, internet and researches etc.

Method of Data Analysis

To achieve the stated objective of this study, data generated was analyzed through the use of descriptive statistics such as measure of central tendencies, which comprise mean, mode, standard deviation, frequency distribution and %ages and inferential statistics(. regression analysis, cost and return analysis, and Gini coefficient.)

i) Descriptive Statistic

Objective 1, 2 and 5 were analysed by Descriptive statistics.

ii) Statistical analysis.

Objective 3 was achieved by computing the Gini Coefficient for the market structure and drawing inference from the results. Objective 4 was achieved by calculating the benefit cost ratio, gross margin and net returns of the respondents in the study area. Multiple regression analysis was carried out to test the stated hypothesis.

Gini Coefficient (G.C)

This was used to examine the market structure in the study area, it is represented as:-

$$G.C = 1 - \frac{2}{n} \sum Y_i X_i$$

Where

Y = the %age of rice sellers

X = the cumulative %age of their sales

The Gini coefficient is the rate of the area between the Lorenz curve and the 45⁰c line to the area meter the 45⁰c line. It is also a measure of inequality. If the value of Gini coefficient is greater than 0.35 it is high indicating inequitable

distribution (Dillon and Hardaker, 1993). In others words higher Gini coefficient means higher level of concentration and consequently, high inefficiency in market structure (Afolabi 2007).

The Cost and Return Analysis

Total cost (TC) = variables cost (VC) + fixed cost (FC)

Total revenue (TR) = price per bag of rice x number of bags sold.

$$\text{Benefit cost ratio (BCR)} = \frac{\text{Total revenue}}{\text{Total cost}}$$

The BCR measures the viability of the bus.....

$$\text{Gross margin} = \text{Total revenue} - \text{variable cost}$$

$$\text{Net return} = \text{Gross margin} - \text{fixed cost}$$

$$\text{i.e. Total revenue} - \text{total cost}$$

Or

The Gross margin is given as

$$\text{GM} = \text{GS} - \text{TRC}$$

Where :

GM = Gross margin

GS = Gross sale

TVC = total variable cost

Note: the gross margin analysis was used to determine the profitability of the rice marketing.

The Regression Analysis

The Ordinary Least Square multiple regression analysis (OLS) under the assumption that the data collected fulfilled the multiple regression model.

The linear regression model $Y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{12})$

Where y = Net return (measure in Naira)

X₁ = Cost of purchase (Naira)

X₂ = Transport cost (Naira)

X₃ = Carriage cost (Naira)

X₄ = storage cost (Naira)

X₅ = Tax/Levy-other cost (naira)

X₆ = Years of rice marketing experience (years)

e = Stochastic error term

Three functional forms of the above model were tried viz,

Linear, semi-log, and double log.

The explicit forms of the functional forms were as follows:

Linear function

$$Y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + b_4x_4 + b_5x_5 + b_6x_6 + e$$

Semi Log function

$$Y = b_0 + b_1\text{Log}x_1 + b_2\text{Log}x_2 + b_3\text{Log}x_3 + b_4\text{Log}x_4 + b_5\text{Log}x_5 + b_6\text{Log}x_6 + e.$$

Double Log function

$$\text{Log}Y = b_0 + b_1\text{Log}x_1 + b_2\text{Log}x_2 + b_3\text{Log}x_3 + b_4\text{Log}x_4 + b_5\text{Log}x_5 + b_6\text{Log}x_6 + e.$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

Table 1: discusses the socio-economics characteristics of the respondents this include age sex (Gender), formal education, family size, etc. In regards to the result in table 1 it showed that majority of the marketers are female representing 77.14 % while male represent 22.86 %.

Majority of the respondent are between the ages brackets of 30 – 39years representing 48.57 %, this is closely followed by those between the age bracket of 40 – 49years representing 30.00 %. While those between 50 – 59years and 20 – 29years represent 11.43 % and 10.00 % respectively.

It can be deduced that most of the marketers are in their economic active years.

Table 1: Socio-Economic characteristics Rice Marketers N=70.

Socio-Economic Characteristics	Frequency	percentage
Gender		
Male	16	22.86
Female	54	77.14
Age		
20 - 29	7	10.00
30 - 39	34	48.57
40 - 49	21	30.00
50 – 59	81	11.43
Household size		
1 – 3	20	28.57
4 – 6	34	48.57
7 – 9	12	17.14
10 – 12	04	05.71
Marital Status		
Single	11	15.71
Married	57	81.43
Divorced	02	02.86
Educational level		
No formal education	0	0.00
Primary education	05	07.14
Secondary education	29	41.43
Tertiary education	27	38.57
Adult education	09	12.86
Marketing Experience (years)		
1—5	38	54.29
6—10	27	38.57
11—15	05	7.14

Source: Field Survey, 2011

Majority of the respondents are married, this represent 81.43 %; this is followed by those who are singled representing 15.71 % while those who are divorced represent 2.86 %.

Household size is a very important factor in agricultural activities. The results indicated that majority of the respondent have an household size of between 4 - 6 representing 48.57 %. This is followed by those with family size between 1- 3 persons, representing 28.57 %. However, respondent with 7 – 9 household size represent 17.14 % while those between 10 – 12 persons of the respondent represent 5.71%.

The result in Table 1 also showed that 7.14 % had attended primary school while 41.43 % had secondary education. However, 38.57 % had acquired tertiary education, and only about 12.86 % of the respondents had adult education. This means that majority of the respondent can at least read and write.

The data analysis further showed 54.29% of the marketer had spent between 1 – 5 years in rice business, while 38.57% claimed to have spent between 6-10 years, and 7.14% had spent 11 – 15 year in the rice business.

Table 2: Marketing Functions and Practices of Rice Marketers N=70.

Variables	Frequency	percentage
Source of purchase		
Distributors	48	68.57
Local Market	4	05.71
Importation	9	12.86
No response	9	12.86
Source of capital		
Personal savings	27	38.57
Friends & Relations	07	10.00
Cooperative loans	31	44.29
Bank loans	05	07.1
Means of Transportation		
Vehicle	41	58.57
Motor bike	09	12.86
Bicycle	01	01.43
Wheel barrow	19	27.14
Storage		
Rented shop	64	91.43
Personal/Attachment	04	05.71
No response	02	02.86
Total	70	100.00

Source: Field Survey, 2011

Table 2 showed that the marketers carry out bulk purchase as part of their marketing function, 68.57% purchase their produce from major distributors, while 12.86 % purchase from importers. However 5.71% purchase from the local market. On the issue of capital majority of the respondent (44.29%) source their funds from Cooperative loans, this is closely followed by those who source their funds from personal savings, 38.57%. however those source from friends and relation were 10.00% %, and bank loan source represent 7.14%. This might be due to the fact that the business owners prefer the cooperative loan which is cheaper when compared to bank loan which attracts high interest rate.

Table 2 also showed that the marketers perform transportation function, and doing this 59.14 % of them uses vehicles as means of transport while 25.81 % and 13.98 % respectively opted for wheelbarrows and motor bike. Further data analyses showed that majority (91.43%) of the marketers uses rented shop in the in carrying out storage business while those who use personal homes/attachment (05.71%).

Cost and Return Analysis

Cost and return analysis helps us in analyzing the profitability of the rice marketers.

Total cost TC = variable cost (VC) + fixed cost (FC)

Total revenue (TR) = price per bag of rice x Number of bags sold.

$$\text{Benefit cost ratio (BCR)} = \frac{\text{Total Revenue}}{\text{Total Cost}}$$

Table 3. Costs and Returns of Respondents

Items	Amount	% of TC	% of Total revenue
Cost of purchase	206,721,470.00	97.90	89.10
Transportation cost	838,910.00	0.0040	0.0036
Cost of carriage	1,115,990.00	0.0053	0.0048
Storage cost	334,500.00	0.0018	0.0014
Tax/levy	50,600.00	0.0024	0.0002
Total variable cost (TVC)	211,108,700.00	99.98	90.99
Total cost (TC)	211,159,300.00	100	91.02
Total revenue (TR)	232,002,400.00		
Total variable cost/seller	3,015,838.57		
Total cost/seller	3,016,561.43		
Total revenue/seller	3,314,320.00		
Gross margin/seller	298,481.43		
Net revenue/seller	297,758.57		
Benefit/cost ratio (BCR)	1.10		

Source: Field survey, 2011

Table 3 shows the cost and return analysis of the respondent revealed the above monthly cost and return based on an average bases. Revenue and cost had to be calculated based on baskets.

The results revealed that cost of purchase accounted for 97.90 % of the total cost, while transportation cost, carriage cost, storage cost, and levy/tax accounted for 0.004 %, 0.0053 %, 0.0018%, and 0.002 % respectively. Further results also cost of purchase accounted for 89.10 % of the total revenue while transportation cost took 0.0036 %, the cost of storage accounted for 00014 %, carriage cost accounts for 0.0014% while tax/levy accounted for 0.002 %.

The profitability analysis shows that on the average, a marketer incurred a total variable cost of N3, 015,838.57 per month. But earned average an revenue of N3, 314,320.00 per month. The result further shows that an average marketer earned N298,481.43 as gross margin per month suggesting that rice marketing is a profitable business (enterprises) in the study area.

The Table 4 also shows the benefit to cost ratio (BCR) = 1.10. The BCR indicate that rice marketing is viable in the study area.

Market structure of Respondent

The value of Gini-Coefficient greater than 0.35 are high indicating inequitable distribution of income/sales (Dillon and Hardaker 1993). The Gini-Coefficient for rice marketers in the study area shown in Table 4.i.e. 0.7629 indicates high level of concentration and consequently high inefficiency in the market structure. This further implies that there is high level of inequality in the sale revenue of respondents and consequently high level of concentration existence of non – competitive labour as collusion. This is a reflection of the effectively of the inefficiency in the market structure for the formula in the study area. This result is corroborated by Afolabi (2007), Afolabi(2009) and Ekunwe and Alufohai (2008) on their study of egg ,garri and egg marketing in south –western region and Benin City in Edo State respectively. While Akarue and Okomunu (2011) on the marketing of tomato in Ika North East L.G.A of Delta state. Afolabi (2007) recorded a Gini coefficient of 0.87692 while Ekunwe and Alufohai (2008) reported a Gini coefficient of 0.81296. However, Onu and Hiyasu (2008) also noted that the food grain in Adamawa State was highly efficient in the operation with operation efficiency of 254.7 %.

Table 4 Computation of Gini Coefficient for Rice Marketers in Udu Local Government Area of Delta State.

Range of income (sales)	Number of seller / frequency	Proportion of seller (x)	Cumulated proportion	Cumulative frequency	Total sales (₦)	Proportion of sales	Cumulative proportion sales (Y)	XY
≤ 1,000,000	34	0.49	0.49	34	10,861,500	0.05	0.05	0.0245
1,000,001-2,000,000	8	0.11	0.60	42	10,399,000	0.04	0.09	0.0099
2,000,001-3,000,000	12	0.17	0.77	54	28,696,600	0.12	0.21	0.0357
3,000,001-4,000,000	1	0.01	0.78	55	3,245,200	0.01	0.22	0.0022
4,000,001-5,000,000	4	0.06	0.84	59	17,623,600	0.08	0.30	0.0048
>5,000,000	11	0.16	1.00	70	161,176,500	0.07	1.00	0.1600
Total	70	1			232,002,400	1		0.2371

Source: Field survey, 2011

Mean value of sales = ₦3, 314,320

Gini coefficient = $1 - (\sum XY) / (\sum X)(\sum Y)$ = $1 - (0.2371) / (1)(1)$ = 0.7629

H₀: there is no significant relationship between Rice marketing cost and return of respondent.

Linear Regression Result

Based on some econometric considerations such as number of significant variables, the F – ratio and the R² value, the linear functional form was selected as the lead equation.

Table 5 . Regression results

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		
1 (Constant)	197778.339	438212.140	.451	.653
COSTOFPURCHASE	.635	.082	7.733	.000*
COSTOFTRANSPORT	62.381	24.259	2.571	.012
COSTOFCARRAGE	68.356	11.031	6.197	.000*
COSTOFSTORAGE	19.516	99.097	.197	.845
OTHERCOST	115.014	186.872	.615	.540
MARKET.EXP	-132362.229	71996.056	-1.838	.071
R ²	0.944			
R ² (Adjusted)	0.938			
F -value	176.009*			
Durbin Watson	2.014			

The equation is thus written as ;

$$Y = 197778.39 + 0.64x_1 + 62.38x_2 + 68.38x_3 + 19.52x_4 + 115.01x_5 - 132362.23x_6$$

N.B* significant at 5%.

Result of the analysis revealed that X_1 (cost of purchase), X_2 (cost of transportation) X_3 (cost of carriage) , X_4 (storage cost)and X_5 (other cost) were positively related to sale revenue. Thus, 0.64, 62.38, 68.38, 19.52, and 115.01 unit increase each in $X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4,$ and X_5 will bring about one unit increase respectively in respondent sale revenue, despite this it is only cost of purchase, transportation cost and carriage cost that are significant at 5%..

On the other hand variable X_6 , (years of marketing) was found to be negatively related to sale revenue. That 132362.23 unit increase in each of X_6 null result in corresponding one unit decrease. Some of this findings corroborate those of (Ezeh 2007; Nwakpu, 2007; Agwu, 2009; and Agwu and Ibeabuchi, 2010.)

The R^2 value of 0.944 means that the estimated variable included in the model explained 94.45% of variation in sale revenue of the respondents. The F- value of 176.009 is also significant at 5%. This finding was similar to that of Akarue and Okomunu (2010) on the marketing of tomato in Ika North east local Government area of Delta state.

Problems Encountered by Marketers

Despite the profitability and viability of the respondent there are still some problems militating against their marketing activities.

Table 6: Constraints /Problem Encountered by Marketers

Problems Encountered	MEAN	Rank
Seasonality of price (price fluctuation)	4.96	1 st
Pest	3.93	4 th
Lack of finance	4.39	2 nd
High transportation cost	4.07	3 rd
High labour cost	3.89	5 th

Source: .Field survey, 2011.

As a decision rule any mean value above 3.0 is accepted and less than 3.0 is rejected.

The major problems encountered by the marketers were analyzing in Table 6, the result showed that all factor problems in rice marketing were considered serious. These problems identified by respondents were ranked in the following order. Price fluctuation (4.96), lack of finance (4.39), High transportation cost (4.07) , pest (3.93) and high labour cost(3.89). Madukue (1993) noted on the issue of lack of finance, He noted that wealth and adoption of innovation go hand in hand. This finding also corroborates the finding of Oladejo and Sanusi (2008) that lack of finance, deterioration in quality of produce, and high cost of transportation representing 30%, 23% and 28% respectively given a cumulative of 81% in regards to plantain marketing.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings in this research work, in the study area, the age distribution shows that the active age groups that dominate the marketing of rice are between 30 to 50 years and they are females and mainly married.

Distribution of respondent by household shows that the households of between 1 and 3 persons dominate the rice marketing and they are mainly tertiary in terms of education. Their source of capital is mainly on cooperatives. Findings also disclosed that those that have been in the business between 1 and 5 years ago dominate the marketing structure of rice in the study area. The marketers rely on vehicles as a means of transport and store their goods in rented shop with very few %ages having their own stores. The sellers buy from distributors and importers. Finally all the factors in relation to problems of marketing were considered serious with mean above 3.0; this includes lack of finance, price fluctuation, High transportation cost, pest and high labour cost.

One can say without mincing words that rice marketing can serve as one of the veritable venture to alleviate poverty in the study area.

RECOMMENDATION

The government should improve in the construction of good roads network in the rural areas to link the village markets and the towns for easy transportation and thereby reducing cost.

The government should expand her micro-finance scheme and make loan accessible to the marketers and likewise other environmental factors that will make it conducive for the marketers to do business..

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